

SECONDARY WAYS OF WORDFORMATION

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Annotation: This resource delves into the fascinating realm of secondary methods employed in the creation of words. While primary word formation involves the construction of words through prefixes, suffixes, and root words, secondary methods introduce alternative pathways for expanding a language's lexicon. The annotation explores various secondary techniques, including compounding, blending, acronym formation, and conversion.

Keywords: Word Formation, Morphology, Lexicon, Linguistics, Secondary, Methods, Compounding, Blending, Acronym Formation, Conversion, Lexical, Evolution, Language Dynamics, Creative Language Use, Neologism, Lexical, Innovation, Grammatical Transformation, Vocabulary Diversity, Morphological, Processes, Wordplay, Linguistic Adaptation, Novel Terminology, Lexical, Hybridization, Linguistic Innovation, Semantic Shift, Language Evolutionary, Trends, Grammatical Categories, Language Enrichment, Terminological, Development, Lexical Diversity, Linguistic Creativity, Etymology, Word, Construction, Derivation, Semantic Change, Lexical Semantics, Language,

Minor types of word making.

Shortening (or clipping) is the word formation process which consists in the reduction of a word to one of its parts (Marchand, 1969). Shortening is also a very productive way of building words in English. New words formed by shortening appear continuously. Shortening is especially productive in colloquial speech and advertisement. It can be considered a good way of creating roots (root morphemes) since new morphemes are used as free roots and can take endings, e.g. *exam, flu, ad, bike, fridge, movie, TV, V-day, smog, brunch*.

The following are the specific types of shortening.

Acronyms: are words built from the initial letters of multiword expressions and read as regular words, e.g. *NATO(BMT) /'nei təu/* (North Atlantic Treaty Organization), *UNO* (United Nations Organization), *BBC* (The British Broadcasting Corporation), *VOA* (the Voice of America), *UNESCO* (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization), *VIP* (a very important person), *PM* (Prime Minister), *MP* (Member of Parliament), *OPEC* (Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries), *AIDS* (Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome), *AWOL* (absent without leave), etc.

It is interesting to include here two special cases of acronyms: monograms and homonymy-based acronyms. Monograms are two or more letters combined in one design. They are usually used in handkerchiefs, notepaper and in Vietnam, very common in wedding invitation cards. Homonymy-based acronyms are based on the use of identical sounds of words and letters, e.g. *I. O. U* (I owe you), *CU* (see you), *HAND* (Have a nice day), *NGU* (Never give up), *DIY* (Do it yourself), *MNOP* (Meet now or pause), *WYSIWYG* (What you see is what you get), *PTO* (Please turn over), *BBL* (Be back later), *MIA* (missing in action), *ASAP* (as soon as possible), *P.S.* (An abbreviation for postscript), *SOS* (save our ship or soul) etc.

Computer and internet acronyms: DVD, (Digital Versatile Disc), GIF (Graphic Interchange Disc), JPEG (Joint Photographic Expert Format), RAM (Random Access Memory), WiFi (Wireless Fidelity), etc.

Clipping

Clipping- also called transaction or shortening is word formation by removing some sigments of an existing word to create a synonym. Clipping consists in the cutting off of one or several syllables of a word. In many cases the stressed syllables are preserved. There is some types of it:

- Initial clipping: the first part of a word is clipped: *phone (mobile phone), car(motor-car), plane(aeroplane), cast (broadcast)*.
- Final clipping: the last part of a word is clipped: *exam, lab, sis, uni, prof*.
- Initio - final clipping: both the first and the last parts are clipped: *fridge, fly, etc*.
- Medial clipping: the medial part is clipped: *maths, specs, V-day, H-bomb*.
- Elliptico - conversional clipping (phrasal clipping: this is a special case in which there is a combination of ellipsis, conversion and clipping, e.g. *sitdown* (a sitdown demonstration); *pop* (popular music); *pub* (public house); *perm* (permanent wave); *prelim* (preliminary examination)

Clippings do not always coincide in meaning with the original word. For example. "doc" and "doctor" have the meaning one who practises medicine, but doctor is also the highest degree given by a university to a scholar or scientist and a person who has received such a degree whereas doc is not used with these meanings. Among abbreviations there are homonyms. One and the same sound and graphical complex may be different words. For example. vacation; vacvacuum cleaner; prep-preparation; prep-preparatory school. In abbreviations we stress each letter. For example. TUC ['ti:'ju:'si:]—Trade Union Congress. If they are pronounced in accordance with the phonetics we stress the first syllable.

For example. NATO t'neitou], UNO ['ju:nou] BBC — British Broadcasting Corporation, Cent—Centigrade. AP—Associated Press, GPO—General Post Office, USA—United States of America, UNESCO—United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization, USAF—United States Air Force, WFDY— World Federation of Democratic Youth, WFTU—World Federation of Trade Unions, SEATO—South-East Asia Treaty Organization, UK—United Kingdom, NAS—National Academy of Sciences, NY—New York, NZ—New Zealand, MD—Doctor of Medicine, FAP—First Aid Post. sub (submarine), surg (surgeon), Sept (September), Serg (sergeant), esp (especially), capt (captain), lat (latitude), Wash (Washington), Wed (Wednesday), usu (usually), pref (preface), prof (professor), prox (proximo), mos (months), quot (quotation), revs (revolutions), Russ (Russian), sat (Saturday), vol (volume), rep (representative), suppl (supplement).

Blending.

Blending is the formation of a new word by a connection of parts of two words to form one word. **For example.** The noun «smog» is composed of the parts of nouns «smoke» and «fog» (sm (oke+f) og. The result of blending is an unanalysable simple word. We do not analyse the blended words (sm-r-og) because their parts can't be called morphemes. **For example.** clash-clap'crash; flush-flash H-blush,1 slanguage=slang+language, brunch- breakfast+lunch, smare-smoke+haze, seadrome=-sea+airdrome). There are many blends in the terminological vocabulary. **For example.** racon-radar+beacon, transceiver-transmitter+receiver. Blending

can be considered ... as the method of merging (connecting) parts of words into one new word as when «sm+oke» and «fog» derived from «smog». Thus, blending is compounding by means of curtailed (shortened) words. However, the clusters «sm» and «og» were morphemes only for the individual speaker who blended them while in terms of the linguistic system as recognized by the community, there are not signs at all. Blending, therefore, has no grammatical, but a stylistic status. The result of blending is ... an unanalysable, simple word, not a motivated syntagma.

Blends are also words formed from a word-group or two synonyms. In blends two ways of word-building are combined: abbreviation and composition. To form a blend we clip the end of the first component (apocope) and the beginning of the second component (apheresis). As a result we have a compoundshortened word. One of the first blends in English was the word «smog» from two synonyms: smoke and fog which means smoke mixed with fog. From the first component the beginning is taken, from the second one the end, «o» is common for both of them. Blends formed from two synonyms are: slanguage, to hustle, gasohol etc. Mostly blends are formed from a word-group, such as : acromania (acronym mania), cinemadict (cinema adict), chunnel (channel, canal), dramedy (drama comedy), detectifiction (detective fiction), faction (fact fiction) (fiction based on real facts), informercial (information commercial) , Medicare (medical care) , magalog (magazine catalogue) slimnastics (slimming gymnastics), sociolite

(social elite), slanguist (slang linguist), *brunch* (from breakfast & lunch), *smog* (smoke & fog), *motel* (motor & hotel), *subtopia* (suburban & utopia), *moped* (motor-assisted pedal-cycle), *heliport* (place where helicopters take off and land), *muppet* (marionette + puppet), *numeracy* (literacy + numbers: good basic knowledge of mathematics), *blog* (web + log), *high-tech* (high + technology), *staycation*(stay + vacation), *emoticon* (emotion + icon), *sitcom* (situation + comedy), *spam* (spiced + ham), *chunnel* (channel + tunnel), *aerobicize* (aerobics + exercise), *bit* (binary + digit), *Reaganomics*, *Oxbridge*, *netizen*, *infotainment*, *medicare*, *Brexit*, *Sci-fi*, *infotech*, etc. Obviously, the mechanism of blending is characterized by certain productivity, which is well demonstrated by such new coinages as rockumentary, infomercial, etc., and is indicative of the tendency towards brief expression and multiplicity of notions fusing to form a complex one.

Sound Imitation

It is the way of word-building when a word is formed by imitating different sounds. There are some semantic groups of words formed by means of sound imitation

- a) sounds produced by human beings, such as: to whisper, to giggle, to mumble, to sneeze, to whistle etc.
- b) sounds produced by animals, birds, insects, such as: to hiss, to buzz, to bark, to moo, to twitter etc.
- c) sounds produced by nature and objects, such as: to splash, to rustle, to clatter, to bubble, to ding-dong, to tinkle etc.

The corresponding nouns are formed by means of conversion, e.g. clang (of a bell), chatter (of children) etc.

Sound Interchange

Sound interchange is an alternation in the phonetic composition of the root, **For example.** food (*n*)—feed (*v*), speak (*v*)—speech (*n*), strong (*adj*)—strength (*n*). Sound interchange may

be considered as a way of forming words only diachronically because in Modern English we can't find a single word which can be formed by changing the root-vowel of a word or by shifting the place of the stress. Sound interchange is non-productive. Sound interchange may be divided into vowel interchange and consonant interchange. **For example.** full—to fill, food—to feed, blood—to bleed, stronger—strength. Here we have vowel interchange and by means of vowel interchange we can distinguish different parts of speech. There are some examples of consonant interchange: advice—to advise, use [ju:z]— to use [ju:z], speak—speech, break—breach, defence—defend, offence— offend. The scientist argue that sound interchange is the way of word-building when some sounds are changed to form a new word. It is non-productive in Modern English, it was productive in Old English and can be met in other Indo-European languages.

The causes of sound interchange can be different. It can be the result of Ancient Ablaut which cannot be explained by the phonetic laws during the period of the language development known to scientists., For example to strike - stroke, to sing - song etc. It can be also the result of Ancient Umlaut or vowel mutation which is the result of palatalizing the root vowel because of the front vowel in the syllable coming after the root (regressive assimilation), For example hot - to heat (hotian), blood - to bleed (blodian) etc. In many cases we have vowel and consonant interchange. In nouns we have voiceless consonants and in verbs we have corresponding voiced consonants because in Old English these consonants in nouns were at the end of the word and in verbs in the intervocal position, For example bath - to bathe, life - to live, breath - to breathe etc.

Stress interchange

Stress interchange can be mostly met in verbs and nouns of Romanic origin: nouns have the stress on the first syllable and verbs on the last syllable, **For example.** 'accent - to accent. This phenomenon is explained in the following way: French verbs and nouns had different structure when they were borrowed into English, verbs had one syllable more than the corresponding nouns. When these borrowings were assimilated in English the stress in them was shifted to the previous syllable (the second from the end). Later on the last unstressed syllable in verbs borrowed from French was dropped (the same as in native verbs) and after that the stress in verbs was on the last syllable while in nouns it was on the first syllable. As a result of it we have such pairs in English as : to con"flikt- "conflict, to ex'port -'export, to ex'tract - "extract etc. As a result of stress interchange we have also vowel interchange in 56 such words because vowels are pronounced differently in stressed and unstressed positions.

Backformation

It is the way of word-building when a word is formed by dropping the final morpheme to form a new word. It is opposite to suffixation, that is why it is called back formation. At first it appeared in the language as a result of misunderstanding the structure of a borrowed word. Prof. Yartseva¹ explains this mistake by the influence of the whole system of the language on separate words. **For example.** it is typical of English to form nouns denoting the agent of the action by adding the suffix -er to a verb stem (speak-speaker). So when the French word «beggar» was borrowed into English the final syllable «ar» was pronounced in the same way as the English -er and Englishmen formed the verb «to beg» by dropping the end of the noun. Other examples of back formation are: to accreditate (from accreditation), to bach (from

¹ В.И.Ярцева. Развитие национального литературного английского языка. Москва.1968

bachelor), to collocate (from collocation), to enthuse (from enthusiasm), to compute (from computer), to emote (from emotion) to reminisce (from reminiscence), to televise (from television) etc. As we can notice in cases of back formation the part-of-speech meaning of the primary word is changed, verbs are formed from nouns. Thus, The term «backformation» has a diachronic relevance (historical meaning). **For example.** The nouns beggar, butler, cobbler, typewriter are very much like the nouns actor, painter, teacher, which have the suffixes -er, -or. On the analogy of the derivatives teacher, speaker, reader the words beggar, butler, cobbler, typewriter etc. synchronically are derived from to beg, to butle, to cob, to typewrite, because we do not feel any difference between the relationship «speak—speaker» and «beg—beggar». But if we study their origin we see butle was derived from «butler». So backformation «denotes the derivation of new words by subtracting a real or supposed affix from existing words through misinterpretation of their structure. . . . Backformation is in fact an example of analogy: the speaker knows pairs like rob /robber and drink/ drinker and when he hears the word «beggar» he makes it conform to the pattern by inventing a form «*beg*». Another well-known historical example of back-formation in English is the verb «*to sidle*», from the adverb «*sideling*».

Backformation is not of the vocabulary, but there ration in our times. One is automatic machinery into from the noun «automation» inflate—inflation, meditatetion» is itself a new word, matic» (Charles Barber). much importance in the growth are a few examples of its the verb «automate», introduce (an industry, a factory), formed on the analogy of such pairs a — meditation; the noun «automa-presumably formed from «auto

Eponymy

Eponymy-is a process of creating new words by using proper names as (mostly) common nouns, e.g. *biro* [ball-point pen] named after Laszlo Biro, its Hungarian inventor; *wellingtons* (after the Duke of Wellington), *braille* [name of a raised writing system used by blind people] from the name of its French inventor, Louis Braille. A number of words in English have originated from the names of people, e.g. *watt* [unit of power] from the 18th century Scottish inventor, James Watt; *boycott* [refuse to deal with or a refusal to deal with] after a landlord in Ireland who made himself unpopular by his treatment of his tenants and was socially isolated; *saxophone* [musical instrument] invented by the Belgian, Adolphe Sax; *mentor* [loyal and wise adviser] from Mentor, friend to Odysseus, etc. Sometimes, an eponym is created by adding a suffix to the proper name, e.g. by adding the suffix *-ism* - *Stalinism*, *Leninism*, *Maoism*, etc., or it becomes a different word class, e.g. by adding the suffixes *-ize*, *-ian*, etc. - to *pasteurize* (the French scientist Louis Pasteur), *Victorian* (after Queen Victoria), etc.

Quite a few names of types of clothing, particularly hats, originate from the people who invented them or made them popular, e.g. *bowler*, *triby*, *cardigan*, *busby*, *wellingtons* or *wellies*, *stetson*, *mackintosh* or *mac*, *leopard*, etc. A number of other words in English come from place names, e.g. *bedlam*, *Spartan*, *canter*, *gypsy*, etc.

Reduplication

Reduplication is a word-formation process in which two phonetically similar or identical morphemes or pseudo-morphemes are combined. Reduplication can be considered to be a special kind of compounding, although the individual components of reduplicatives are often meaningless and emotionally/ stylistically colored. Reduplicatives may be divided into **rhyiming** (e.g. *hocus-pocus*, *walkie-talkie*, *hurry-scurry*, etc.) and **non-rhyiming** (e.g. *tip-top*,

chit-chat, zigzag, etc.), or **full** (the two morphemes are identical in every aspect), e.g. *chop-chop, goody-goody, no-no, poo-poo, bye-bye, etc.* and **partial** (the two morphemes are not identical), e.g. *sing-song, tittle-tattle, hoity-toity, etc.*

Conclusion

In English language teaching and learning, having a good demand of lexicology in general and word-formation or word-building in particular is of great importance. The above ten ways of word-formation (affixation, compounding, shortening, sound imitation, conversion, back-derivation, sound & stress interchange, eponymy and reduplication) can be a great help for learners and teachers when learning and teaching English so that they can use the language to communicate correctly, effectively and flexibly.

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